

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN LOGISTIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The application of Information Technologies (IT) in logistic systems has significantly transformed the management and optimization of logistics processes, including transportation, distribution, storage, and inventory management. This paper explores the key information technologies reshaping the logistics industry, focusing on their role in improving efficiency, customer satisfaction, and competitiveness, as well as their potential for future advancements in logistics operations.

Keywords: Information Technology, Logistic Systems, Transportation Management Systems, Warehouse Management, Supply Chain Management, Real-Time Monitoring.

Аннотация

Применение информационных технологий (ИТ) в логистических системах значительно изменило управление и оптимизацию логистических процессов, включая транспортировку, распределение, хранение и управление запасами. В данной работе рассматриваются ключевые информационные технологии, которые трансформируют логистическую отрасль, с акцентом на их роль в повышении эффективности, удовлетворенности клиентов и конкурентоспособности, а также на их потенциал для будущих усовершенствований в логистических операциях.

Ключевые слова: Информационные технологии, логистические системы, системы управления транспортом, управление складом, управление цепочками поставок, мониторинг в реальном времени.

Introduction

Technologies such as Transportation Management Systems (TMS), Warehouse Management Systems (WMS), and Supply Chain Management Systems (SCM) have become integral in automating and integrating various stages of logistics operations. Real-time monitoring tools like GPS, RFID, and IoT devices enable the continuous tracking of shipments and inventory. Additionally, advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, Blockchain, and Big Data Analytics enhance operational efficiency, reduce costs,

and improve decision-making capabilities. The rise of e-commerce further accelerates the adoption of these technologies, particularly in areas like order fulfillment and last-mile delivery.

Information Technologies in Logistic Systems refers to the application and integration of various information technologies (IT) to optimize and manage logistics processes. These processes include the storage, transportation, distribution, and management of goods and services. By utilizing IT, logistics companies can streamline operations, improve efficiency, and enhance the decision-making process. **Information Systems and Software** include Transportation Management Systems (TMS), Warehouse Management Systems (WMS), Supply Chain Management Systems (SCM), and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems that help automate and integrate different parts of the logistics process.

Real-Time Monitoring and Control: Technologies like GPS tracking, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and RFID tags help monitor the location, condition, and status of shipments and inventory in real-time. IT systems in logistics often include big data analytics, allowing companies to forecast demand, optimize routes, and analyze trends to improve operational efficiency and reduce costs. The rise of e-commerce has transformed logistics by enabling online orders and digital payment systems, requiring new IT solutions for order fulfillment and last-mile delivery. **Blockchain Technology** used for ensuring transparency and security in transactions, contract management, and the tracking of goods within the supply chain.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning help in predicting trends, automating warehouse operations, and optimizing supply chain activities. The use of these technologies in logistics enhances operational effectiveness, reduces errors, cuts costs, and improves overall customer satisfaction.

Methodology

Logistics encompasses the strategic coordination and management of procurement, storage, and transportation processes to ensure that goods are delivered on time and in optimal condition. Effective operations management is crucial in the logistics sector, especially in today's highly competitive global environment, where the execution of efficient and cost-effective operations is paramount.

As outlined by Rouse (2023), logistics is composed of five key elements: storage, materials handling and warehousing, packaging, inventory,

transportation, and information control. Efficient storage, materials handling, and warehousing are vital for manufacturers, yet consumer demand often fluctuates, necessitating the temporary storage of surplus goods. Warehouses, equipped with shelving, racks, and material handling equipment, are essential for this purpose. Proper packaging also plays a critical role in maintaining product quality, and standardized packaging is commonly used to facilitate easier handling. Inventory management is closely linked to warehousing, as it involves controlling the flow of goods into and out of storage. Transportation is a hallmark of logistics, encompassing roadways, railways, shipping, and air travel, which enable the movement of goods, whether perishable items with short supply chains or complex products with global components. Information and control systems are integral to triggering operational procedures, such as warehouse orders and transport plans, ensuring smooth logistics operations (Rouse, 2023). In the era of globalization, the logistics industry faces significant challenges as demand outpaces predictions, driven by emerging technologies that disrupt the market (Muango, Abrokwah, & Qu, 2021). Transportation, service infrastructure, and customs processes within the logistics sector are highly complex, and each country encounters unique challenges shaped by local regulations and market conditions (Wang, Kumar, Kumari, & Kuzmin, 2022). Recent studies highlight the positive impact of information technology (IT) adoption on the logistics sector. For example, Ainomugisha (2022) found that IT implementation leads to reduced shipping and trucking costs, faster delivery, and enhanced logistical capacities. Zainal and Rasi (2021), emphasize the importance of investing in logistics IT to maintain competitiveness and enhance customer engagement. The advent of IT has revolutionized logistics by integrating systems, enhancing communication, and improving organizational efficiency (Winkelhaus & Grosse, 2019). The logistics services market is diverse, encompassing freight movement, compliance, shipping, warehousing, and distribution. Global trade heavily depends on the logistics industry to facilitate the movement of goods, and as globalization increases trade volumes, the demand for warehousing and storage facilities has risen correspondingly. The value of the local warehousing and storage market was estimated at RM 1.82 billion in 2021, with projections reaching RM 3.06 billion by 2027. Logistics is integral to global trade, as highlighted by Wiederer (2023), who stress that the effectiveness of a nation's logistics services influences its ability to participate in the global economy. The logistics industry, particularly its shipping sector, faces challenges such as government bureaucracy, infrastructure constraints, and the

need for technological and operational improvements (Lezhnina & Balykina, 2021; UNCTAD, 2021). Efficiency is central to logistics operations, providing a competitive edge through advanced technologies like on-time shipping, zero cargo damage, and cost minimization (Gavalas, Syriopoulos, & Roumpis, 2022; Gunasekaran et al., 2017). Logistics industry is undergoing a transformation driven by IT, with companies adopting advanced technologies to improve performance and efficiency (Othman, 2020). IT advancements, including QR codes, barcode systems, mobile applications, and RFID, offer significant potential for enhancing logistics operations. However, despite the increased adoption of IT in logistics, there remains a need for further research on its impact on Malaysian logistics companies (Ainomugisha, 2022).

Information Technology Information technology (IT) is a critical component influencing human life, economic relations, and societal well-being. IT in the workplace and daily life involves collecting, processing, storing, and transmitting data or providing access to information through various tools, including electronics and optics. Technological advancements have led to significant transformations across many industries, making processes faster and more efficient (Ganguly, 2023).

Information Technology in Logistic Industry Information technology plays a crucial role in the logistics industry by enabling companies to manage the flow of goods efficiently. The industry involves the use of machines, vehicles, and computer applications to ensure that manufacturing and production are completed as quickly and efficiently as possible. The logistics industry's highly complex nature requires continuous optimization of technology to meet the rising demand for global commodity transport. IT impacts logistics by enhancing efficiency, improving competitiveness, and promoting sustainability. IT in logistics includes management systems, virtualization, automation tools, operating systems, system software, and critical applications. User peripherals, devices, and software are also integral to IT in logistics. Data storage and utilization methods, architectures, and laws are considered part of IT. Chung (2021) identifies several logistics technologies, including blockchain, big data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), automating warehouses, autonomous vehicles, and sustainability through technology. Examples of IT application in the logistics industry include:

- FedEx : In 2019, FedEx introduced its autonomous delivery robot, Roxo, in New York, although the project was halted by the city's mayor (Vincent, 2022).

- Amazon: Amazon tested its autonomous delivery robot, Scout, in Washington and California in 2019, with the aim of providing one-day delivery for Amazon Prime customers (Salinas, 2019).

- Alibaba: In 2020, Alibaba launched Xiaomanlv, an autonomous logistics robot that can deliver 500 parcels daily and travel 100km on a single charge.

Logistics industry also embraces automation and digital technology to enhance service efficiency and output. Intelligent logistics integrates business and information flows, creating a modern logistics and information processing center. Technologies like Electronic Data Interchange (EDI), barcode, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Management Information Systems (MIS), Global Positioning System (GPS), Geographic Information System (GIS), and others provide accurate and timely logistical services. Westport Malaysia, for instance, has invested in digital solutions, including its Remote Physical Check System (RPS), which improves accuracy and reduces waste by allowing remote verification processes (Shahril, 2023). NinjaVan, another logistics company in Malaysia, is adopting green energy electric vehicles and innovative packaging solutions like "Ninja Packs," which use QR codes and barcodes for secure and efficient delivery (Oriental Daily, 2022) Information Technology Integration The integration of information technology into a firm's management system has been crucial for enhancing operational efficiency (Ainomugisha, 2022). Yang et al (2021), emphasize that the core of production transformation and the digitalization of processes has been a focal point in numerous studies, highlighting technology's positive impact on company performance. However, other research underscores the significance of organizational characteristics within the administrative and managerial sectors, suggesting that the effective application of organizational principles may be a prerequisite for the successful implementation of technological innovations. The relationship between organizational and technical elements, and their combined contribution to company performance, has been explored from various angles. The complex interplay between technical and organizational factors carries significant implications for maintaining a competitive advantage. The execution of organizational strategies is particularly crucial in sustaining this edge (James & Inyang, 2022). However, there are notable distinctions between small and large enterprises, with smaller businesses often being less informed of market changes (James & Inyang, 2022). The incorporation of information technology offers several benefits, including expanding market share, achieving economies of scale and scope, and facilitating the dissemination of innovative ideas across

the logistics process. Additionally, IT enhances the flexibility of routing across different transportation modes and enables door-to-door transportation services (Rey et al., 2021).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the integration of Information Technologies (IT) into logistic systems has proven to be a game-changer for the logistics industry, driving significant improvements in operational efficiency, cost reduction, and customer satisfaction. Technologies such as Transportation Management Systems (TMS), Warehouse Management Systems (WMS), and Supply Chain Management (SCM) systems enable seamless integration and automation of logistics processes, while tools like GPS, RFID, and the Internet of Things (IoT) allow for real-time monitoring and enhanced visibility. The adoption of advanced technologies, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, Blockchain, and Big Data Analytics, has further optimized decision-making, enabling companies to adapt quickly to market changes and meet the growing demands of e-commerce. As the logistics industry continues to evolve, the ongoing development and application of these IT solutions will play a crucial role in shaping the future of logistics, ensuring greater efficiency, sustainability, and competitiveness in an increasingly globalized market.

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